

Exploring the Islamic Legal Framework for Women Participation in Politics

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Abstract

This paper examines the Islamic perspective on women's participation in politics. To achieve this, the paper provides an overview of the Islamic legal framework that governs and influences women's involvement in politics as well as the political rights of women. The paper observes that Islamic jurisprudence, which underpins legal and ethical issues, anchors basic ideas and interpretations of the role of women in governance and political involvement. It is against this background that the paper argues the dominance of men in the political world, leaving women susceptible to harassment and persecution under the guise of Sharia law. The lacuna discovered during this interrogation justifies the recommendations that the paper has made. Meanwhile, the paper adopts the Qualitative Research Method (QRM) with phenomenological design. The QRM enables proper examination of the Islamic scriptural provisions on the concept of women participation in politics. Data was collected mainly through focus group discussions, newspapers and journals. The data collected can be categorized into primary and secondary sources.

Keywords: Politics, Women, Islamic legal framework and Gender equality

Introduction

Politics allows people to fulfil some of their societal responsibilities. Voting in elections, working as a legislator, a judge, or heading one of the executive branches are all ways to participate in the political system. Gender equality is a valued concept globally. However, cultural and social norms especially in Africa among which is Nigeria, have denied women of equal opportunities in the political space. Within the social sciences, politics focuses on the principles and foundations of government, international relations, organizations, and governmental policies.¹ Sharia, or Islamic jurisprudence, is the fundamental legal and ethical supporting for Muslims. There are basic ideas and interpretations within the Islamic jurisprudence framework that address the role of women in governance and political involvement. However, Rahman and Memon noted that 'in Islam, there is no such provision that women cannot participate in politics and hold position.'² To buttress this point, Rahman and Memon averred that:

The process through which the leader of an Islamic State is confirmed by the people is known as Bai'ah, which is a symbolic agreement or bond between the leader and the people wherein the leader promises to follow and observe Islamic laws and the people in return, promise their faithfulness towards him. Therefore, Bai'ah can be considered the election of the leader as without it the supposed leader has no legitimacy and cannot perform as the head of the state. Prophet Muhammad was reported to receive the Bai'ah from women....³

In the pre-Islamic era, women were seen as source of shame. However, during the Islamic era, Prophet Muhammad promoted the oneness of God and equality that emphasize distinction of tribe, family and ancestry. Yamani noted that Muslim women accompanied Muslim men on their immigration to Abyssinia. He also averred that this era heralded the start of the Madinan period, which gave rise to the first Muslim state and society as well

as the first social and legal revolution that elevated women to a position never before seen in Arabia.⁴ Prophet Muhammad brought changes that improved the social and legal standing of women compared to the prevailing norms in the Arabian Peninsula. Khadijah the wife of the Prophet was a successful businesswoman who owned investments. Similarly, Islam promoted the quest for knowledge, and women were encouraged to seek knowledge. Prominent female scholars, such as Aisha the youngest wife of Prophet Muhammad, were known for their expertise in various fields, including Islamic jurisprudence and hadith.

Also, Umm Salama was known for her political insight and Muslim leaders used to seek her advice on social matters. It is widely believed that both soft and hard elements are required in politics to make sound decisions. In line with this claim, the world has witnessed more involvement of women in politics. The “Women in politics: 2023” map, created by the Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU) and UN Women indicated that women are underrepresented at all levels of decision-making worldwide and that achieving gender parity in political life is far off. It also observed that women serve as heads of state and/or government in only 31 countries. Women comprise 26.5% of members of Parliament. Globally, less than one in four Cabinet Ministers is a woman (22.8 per cent).⁵ Nkereuwem averred that ‘women’s representation in Nigerian politics has been on a downward slide since 2011, and the 2023 elections.’⁶ It was observed that out of the aforementioned statistics of women participation in politics, very few of the women are Muslims. This backfall was noted to be as a result of religious belief arising from contentious matters in the Islamic jurisprudence framework regarding women participation in social responsibilities.

Women's political participation is undeniably an important component of modern democratic countries. It broadens perspectives, improves decision-making processes, and strengthens government legitimacy. However, in some African countries, particularly Nigeria, cultural and religious traditions have created impediments to women's active participation in politics. This was noted to inhibit Muslim women from participating in government, depriving society of women's competence. Scholars have made several attempts to explore the Islamic perspective on the extent to which a woman should participate in politics and governance. However, little or no attention was given to the contentious juristic principles by the various schools of thought. Accordingly, this paper seeks to examine the Islamic legal framework for women's political participation, focusing on the juristic principles of Islamic jurisprudence. This paper hopes to add to the continuing discussion regarding harmonizing Islamic beliefs with the concepts of gender equality and women's empowerment. Descriptive phenomenological method was adopted for the paper. Ituma noted that ‘descriptive phenomenology of religion seeks to describe accurately the eventful manifestations or religious actions in human experience.’⁷ This method would enable comprehensive exploration of the phenomenon with a social lens.

Overview of Muslim Women Political Activities

Women's roles in Islamic politics have a long and varied history, spanning centuries and changing widely across areas and time periods. Accordingly, an overview of the historical progression of women's involvement in Islamic politics during the early Islamic period and the modern era will be explored.

Muslim Women Political Activities in the Early Islamic Period

During the lifetime of Prophet Muhammad, women played active roles in Islamic community. They were actively involved in social and political matters, and some women, like Khadijah and Aisha, were known for their political insight and contributions to the community. Rahman and Memon noted that ‘in the early Islamic period,

women's views were often listened to, respected, and generally supported, by the Prophet'.⁸ An example of this assertion was at the time of Treaty of *Hudaybia* during which the prophet told the people to shave their heads and offer their sacrifices where they were, however; they refused to follow the orders. He contacted his wife Umm Salmah for advice, and she suggested that he take the lead by first doing it himself. He took her advice, and it worked. Similarly, the Qur'an narrated the story of Queen Bilqees in the land of *Saba* and the way she was in ruling the land. It was reported that 'she seeks advices from her counsellors, on how to deal with the threat of attack by the military of King Solomon'.⁹ This indicates that a woman was at a time superintendent over the affairs of men including warriors. She decides what happens in society on behalf of the people she is ruling. Accordingly, this challenges the perception of feminine natural incapacity. It further connotes human equality between the male and female gender.

Although in the early Islamic period, women were not holding formal political offices such as the Caliphate position, however, they were indirectly highly influential. They provide advice to political leaders and also play essential roles in governance. Trillier averred that 'Arab women held an important political and religious position in early Islam, especially when they belonged to noble families. Women such as Khadija and Aisha the wives of the Prophet Muhammad as well as his daughter Fatima, played a vital role in the Islamic Judicial System.'¹⁰ Khadija for instance, was known as an independent woman who managed her business affairs by herself. She employs men to transact on her behalf. One could deduce that she influenced the economic and social institutions during the early days of Islam. Similarly, Aisha was known as one of the greatest influencers of the educational institution of the earlier Islamic era. She was always referred to, for guidance on domestic and other juristic-related matters. These efforts by those prominent women have helped in shaping the then Islamic society, thereby connoting women as indirect rulers of the society.

Muslim Women Political Activities in the Modern Era

Muslim women's participation in politics during the modern era became more limited, partially due to changing societal norms and interpretations of Islamic law. However, women have continued to participate in various social, educational, and charitable activities. During this period, women, as well as men, became more active in political movements for independence and self-determination. For instance, in the 20th and 21st centuries, there have been notable advancements in women's political participation in several Muslim-majority countries. Women have held top political positions, such as prime ministers and presidents, and have actively participated in political movements advocating for their rights. The extent of their participation varies by region and country. Some of the aspects of Muslim women's political activities in the modern era include:

Voting: Muslim women in various countries have campaigned for and won the right to vote and be voted for. For example, Muslim women in Turkey gained the right to vote in 1934, and women in Pakistan obtained the right to vote in 1947. Wagner noted that 'in Turkey, women had the right to vote in all elections by the mid-1930s; they were also given equal rights in matters of divorce and child custody.'¹¹ While Shami averred that 'with the advent of the Pakistan Movement, women's participation in the freedom struggle became a dire necessity, both for increasing the Muslim vote bank and for showcasing their size during the political gatherings of the Muslim League.'¹² Many Muslim-majority countries have since granted women the right to vote and run for office. In Nigeria, Muslim women began to be active in voting during the 1979 elections, in the northern part of the country.

This is coming at the time of Second Republic when Muslim women were appointed to public position.¹³ In the modern era, Muslim women participation in voting has significantly improved. This is evident in the number of women who decry long queues and sunny days to vote in the recent elections across Africa including Nigeria.

Leadership: Muslim women have broken barriers in the 20th & 21st centuries, by occupying political leadership positions. Notable examples include Ms Amina J. Muhammad who is currently the Deputy Secretary-General of the United Nations and Chair of the United Nations Sustainable Development Group (SDG). Also, there are many Muslim women who have secured roles in national leadership, such as the former Prime Minister of Pakistan, President of Indonesia Megawati, Prime Minister of Turkey, and President of the Republic of Singapore.¹⁴ Similarly, Nigerian Muslim women have had the opportunity of occupying leadership position in the country. Notable among these women are the former chief justice of Nigeria; Justice Aloma Mariam Mukhtar, former Minister of Finance, Budget and National Planning; Zainab Shamsuna Ahmed and the Senator representing Adamawa Central Senatorial District in the 9th Senate and Chairperson Senate Committee on SDG; Senator Aishatu Dahiru Binani. The exemplary performances of the aforementioned Muslim women among others have changed the narrative of the primitive perception about Muslim women's involvement in politics. Thus, more participation of Muslim women in political activities would enhance good governance and totally eradicate patriarchy, thereby promoting gender equality in the society.

Unionism: The objectives of Muslim women within the framework of unionism encompass a broad spectrum of issues, including the pursuit of fair treatment and equal opportunities. They engaged in union activities mainly to raise awareness about the challenges they encounter and to advocate for policy changes at different levels of government. Various networks and organizations, such as the Federation of Muslim Women Association of Nigeria (FOMWAN) provide platforms for Muslim women to engage in political discourse, networking, and activism. Some Muslim women have been active in peace and conflict resolution efforts. Notable examples include Yemeni activist Tawakkol Karman, who won the Nobel Peace Prize for her work in 2011, and Malala Yousafzai, who advocates for girls' education and women's rights. Tawakkol Karman who is known as "The Mother of the Revolution" in Yemen for her impact as a journalist and women's rights advocate.¹⁵ Falola noted that:

Aisha Yesufu a Nigerian Muslim woman has been very consistent and never deviated from the ethos of advocacy and democratic principles which she has come to be identified with. Her involvement in the Bring Back Our Girls movement from 2014 was a revelation of her love for the freedom of the female demographic in Northern Nigeria who have remained victims of systemic rights abuses because of rigid religious views and other practices.¹⁶

Islam and Human Rights

Every person has the right to certain rights, which are commonly known as human rights. In Islam, human rights are deeply entrenched in the concept that God, and God alone, is the giver of life and the source of all human rights. Because they are divine in nature, no ruler, government, assembly, or authority may limit or violate the human rights bestowed by God in any way, nor can they be surrendered. Human rights are universal, and as such, they take precedence above other rights granted to people for other reasons. All humans have equal access to human rights since been human cannot be lost, renounced, or forfeited. The United Nations' 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights is widely regarded as the international standard for human rights. This proclamation, which highlights concepts such as the right to life, liberty, and security, religious freedom, and equality before

the law, has been accepted by many Muslims and Muslim-majority countries. The former United Nation's high Commissioner for Human Rights Alhussein averred that 'all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights.'¹⁷ In Nigeria, Section 33 – 46 of Chapter four of the 1999 constitution was dedicated to the fundamental human rights of a Nigerian. Every citizen of the country regardless of gender, is entitled to these fundamental rights. The position of Islam is not too far from that of the universal human rights. In the Islamic perspective of human rights, all human beings are equal except in the aspect of faith which is determined by God only. The main aspect of human right which Islam emphasized are the right to life, equal treatment, and respect for the chastity of women. These shall be examined subsequently.

The Right to Life: The right to life is the most fundamental of all the rights in Islam. Islam emphasizes the value of human life and provides principles for preserving and protecting it. It was observed that the right to life in Islam is based on verse 5:32 of the Quran which states that 'Whosoever slays a human being without any reason like manslaughter, or mischief on earth, it is as though he slew all mankind'. However, it was noted that there was an exception to this rule as contained in verse 6:151, where it was said that killing a person through the due process of law is permitted. The law referred to in this context is the Sharía, which would make it possible to sentence people to death according to its rules about murder and terrorism among others. Regarding the issue of taking a life in retribution for murder or the penalty for bringing corruption to this planet, it could be decided only by a proper and competent court of law.¹⁸ It could be noted that life is regarded as sacred in the Islamic perspective. Hence, it emphasized protection and preserving human life regardless of gender or social status.

Human Equality: The concept of human equality in Islam is based on the premise that all human beings are equal in God's eyes. Discrimination on the basis of gender, colour, ethnicity, language, or nationality is prohibited, and God has given man the right to equality as a birthright, without specifying gender. Thus, both men and women have equal rights in social responsibilities, economic and religious duties. Article I (a) of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) states thus:

All human beings form one family whose members are united by submission to God and descent from Adam. All men are equal in terms of basic human dignity and basic obligations and responsibilities, without any discrimination on the grounds of race, colour, language, sex, religious belief, political affiliation, social status or other considerations. True faith is the guarantee for enhancing such dignity along the path to human perfection.¹⁹

Patoari noted that Islam does not allow the domination of men over women rather, it upholds the rights, dignity, honour and status of women by ensuring gender equality as well as rights equality for men and women in all spheres of human existence.²⁰ Although it is believed that men and women have different duties and obligations in Islam. However, both are regarded equal in terms of spiritual merit. In areas such as religion, worship, and accountability to God, women have the same rights and obligations as males. These rights, however, may be represented differently in different cultural and societal circumstances. It was observed that Allah (God) often refer to mankind as *Naas* (Mankind) without discriminating male gender from the female gender. Example of this is verse 13 of Chapter 49 of the Quran which states thus: O humanity! Indeed, we created you from a male and a female, and made you into peoples and tribes so that you may get to know one another. Similarly, it was stated in the Hadith (traditions of Prophet Muhammad) that Prophet Muhammad said: "All of you are guardians and are responsible for your subjects. The ruler is a guardian of his subjects, the man is a guardian of his family, the woman is a guardian and is responsible for her husband's house and his offspring; and so, all of you are guardians

and are responsible for your subjects.”²¹ Above mentioned scriptural provisions indicates that Islam sees every human being as equal in rights and responsibilities. Thus, women have equal rights with men except in peculiar matters which are exclusively gender related.

Respect for the Chastity of Women

In Islam, the concept of chastity is highly valued and plays a significant role in the lives of women. It encompasses a range of principles and behaviours that promote respect for the chastity of women. Respect for women's chastity is seen as a key and significant part of Islamic teachings. It highlights the importance of modesty and the safeguarding of women's chastity, particularly in terms of modesty, privacy, and consent. In front of males with whom they may marry, Muslim women are encouraged to dress modestly and cover their bodies, except for their faces and hands. This practice is frequently associated with the use of a hijab (veil). In addition, men are not permitted to access the private quarters of women who are not their close relatives. Furthermore, the concept of consent in marriage is highly valued in Islam. A woman's consent is deemed necessary for a lawful marriage, and forced marriages are not considered valid in Islamic Shari'a.

Contentious Issues on Muslim Women's Participation in Politics

One of the contentious aspects of Islamic Sharia law is the restriction on women holding political office; this is viewed as a blatant infringement on women's rights. It was observed that the main contentious issue in the subject matter is the permissibility of women assuming leadership positions. Some Islamic Jurists asserted that it is prohibited for a woman to occupy political office, citing the opinions of ancient clerics, which unanimously forbid women from assuming leadership, as it is a condition of the Caliph (the ruler of a Muslim community) to be male. The argument for requiring a male leader is based on the belief that leadership, particularly in times of warfare, places significant physical demands on the leader. The Caliph is the commander in battles and on the front lines, which may not align with a woman's physical constitution. The Caliph might have to engage in combat and oversee prolonged periods of warfare, which women might not be suited to endure. Thus, the issue of women assuming any executive position or presidency has become a subject of debate. The argument was noted to be on the woman's inability to handle the responsibilities of leadership due to the strenuous demands and burdens that come with it.

The Islamic scholars who opined the prohibition of female leadership justified the prohibition by referencing a Hadith of Prophet Muhammad concerning the daughter of the Persian King Kisra. When the Prophet was informed that she had assumed leadership, he said, "A people will not succeed if they entrust their affairs to a woman." However, Ibrahim averred that the hadith is specific to Persians under the umbrella of prophecy and not in the domain of passing a legal ruling.²² He further noted that although Islamic jurisprudence contains a principle that considers the generality of the word rather than the specificity of the cause, the Qur'an's acknowledgement that the Queen of Sheba was a wise ruler who led her people to success (both religiously and politically) affirms the specification. It is imperative to note that the nature of leadership has evolved and changed, which means there is no longer a Caliph system of government especially in circular nations like Nigeria. The president or head of government's role and responsibilities today differ from those of the Caliph in the past. The president heads an executive authority bound by laws and a constitution, unlike the Caliph. There are numerous decisive pieces of evidence from both Quran and Hadith of the Prophet that demonstrates women's participation in all political aspects. For instance, the Quran states: "The believing men and believing women are allies of one another. They enjoin what is right and forbid what is wrong."²³ This verse clearly indicates that believing men and women support and protect each other, and both can take on roles and responsibilities in supporting and

protecting one another. Women can support men, and men can support women, and both can assume each other's roles and responsibilities.

Women also participated in the process of legal interpretation known as 'ijtihad', which is the authority to legislate laws in the contemporary sense. They were instrumental in the revelation of new rulings, as evidenced in Chapter 58 of the Quran. In this Chapter, there is a story of a woman who came to Prophet Muhammad, complaining about her husband's expression to her; which implied a form of divorce. The woman continued to insist and raise the issue, signifying her dissatisfaction with the response she got from Prophet Muhammad. Eventually, the Chapter was revealed, and it clarified the rules concerning the matter. This revelation was prompted by the persistence of this woman who argued with the Prophet about her husband's words. Also, it should be noted that the Prophet's biography is full of political events in which women played prominent roles. Foremost among them is Khadijah and Aisha the wives of the Prophet. Furthermore, the Prophet, peace be upon him, did not limit his pledge to men when he intended to migrate to Medina.

Another contentious issue regarding women participation in politics is the fear of unguided mix up of the opposite gender. It was observed that people who have this believe rely on Chapter 33 verse 33 which states that women are to stay at home without displaying allurements as in the former time of ignorance. It was observed also that after the passing of the Prophet, there were numerous stories that indicate women's participation in political life. It is not reported from any of the companions or Caliphs that they disregarded or prevented women from expressing their opinions because of their gender. On the contrary, their opinions were valued and considered within society. It is pertinent to note that Islam have mechanisms and rules that guides the manner of gathering with opposite gender. During the Muslim prayers in the Mosques, it could be observed that women are always behind the men. Also, a shield or barrier is placed to ensure that both genders do not mix up unnecessarily. Chapter 33:53 of the Quran provided adequate guide on how to engage with opposite gender without such mixture that may lead to immorality. Also, the Prophet warned that, no man must be alone with a woman except in the presence of her *Mahram* (close relative). These Quranic provisions have provided a framework upon which relationships between opposite gender will be built in society. They demonstrate Islam's concern for women and their active contribution to public affairs and political work. Thus, women have full rights and are not diminished in status because of their gender. The prohibition by some clerics on women assuming the caliphate is not due to any presumed intellectual deficiency, political incapacity, or leadership incompetence on the part of women. It is primarily based on tasks and responsibilities that may not align with the physical nature of women. Hence, the issue of leadership in modern times, such as the presidency, is different from the historical concept of the Caliphate.

Conclusion

Politics is a means through which people regardless of their gender, fulfil some of their societal responsibilities either by voting in elections or occupying a leadership position. Women are often denied this fundamental human right under the guise of Sharia law/jurisprudence. In the modern democratic dispensation, women's participation in politics is seen as indubitable and undeniably an important component of modern democratic countries. It broadens perspectives, improves decision-making processes, and strengthens government legitimacy. However, in some African countries, particularly Nigeria, cultural and religious traditions have created impediments to women's active participation in politics. This was noted to inhibit Muslim women from participating in government, depriving society of women's competence. Accordingly, this paper explored the Islamic legal framework for women's political participation. It was discovered that during the lifetime of Prophet Muhammad, women played active roles in Islamic community.

They were actively involved in social and political matters, and some women, like Khadijah and Aisha, were known for their political insight and contributions to the community. Also, during the modern era, women have continued to participate in various social, educational, and charitable activities. Some of these activities include voting, leadership and unionism. In the Islamic perspective of human rights, all human beings are equal

except in the aspect of faith which is determined by God only. Islam emphasizes the right to life, equal treatment, and respect for the chastity of women. There are several scriptural provisions which indicates that Islam sees every human being as equal in rights and responsibilities. Thus, women have equal rights with men except in peculiar matters which are exclusively gender related. In the history of Islam, women were influential in legal interpretations and the revelation of new rulings, as evidenced in Chapter 58 of the Quran. The revelation of this Chapter clarified the rules concerning utterances that leads to separation in marriage and the implications. Also, the Prophet's biography was full of political events in which women played prominent roles. Foremost among them was Khadijah and Aisha the wives of the Prophet.

Unguided mixture of male and female is one of the contentious issues in women participation in political activities according to the Islamic worldview. So, some Quranic provisions such as Chapter 33:53 had provided a framework upon which relationship between opposite genders will be built in the society. They demonstrate Islam's concern for women and their active contribution to public affairs and political work. Women have full rights and are not diminished in status because of their gender. Also, the objection on women assuming the Caliphate was discovered to be primarily based on tasks and responsibilities that may not align with the physical nature of women. Therefore, the issue of leadership in modern times, such as the presidency, is different from the historical concept of the Caliphate. Hence, a woman could assume such position observing the Islamic framework on social gathering. Women's participation in politics is a vital aspect of democratic governance and gender equality. It was discovered that Islam laid solid foundations on social responsibilities and also drew attention to the role of women in political activities.

It emphasized their participation in political activities through the Prophet's biography and the history of his Caliphs. Islam granted women full rights to engage in political activities that aligns with their nature and physical constitution. It did not diminish their rights in any way. The restrictions on certain roles are not due to a lack of capability on women's part, as some might suggest, rather stem from considerations of suitability. Just as men may not be suitable for certain tasks that do not align with their physical nature, the same principle applies to women. Accordingly, it is recommended that stake holders should promote refined religious and civic education for women in order to empower them to know their rights. Also, legal systems should be reformed to ensure that both Islamic principles and international human rights standards are considered. In addition, dialogue should be promoted to foster an understanding of the compatibility of Islamic values with women's participation in politics. The media could also play the role of advocacy in order to raise awareness of the importance of women's participation in politics.

Endnotes

¹ D. K. Ologbenla, *Introduction to Political Science*. National Open University of Nigeria Course Guide, 3.

² R. N. Farhana and Memon, K. *Political Participation of Women: Contemporary Perspective of Gender and Islam*. Weber Sociology & Anthropology. 1, no. 1 (2015): 2.

³ Ibid., 1.

⁴ Yamani, A. Z. *Women During the Prophet's Lifetime*, in (ed.). *Woman in Islam*, London, Al-Furqan Islamic Heritage Foundation.

⁵ IPU and UN Women, *Women in Politics: 2023*.

⁶ Nkereuwem, E. *Why Women Haven't Been Successful in Nigerian Elections*.

⁷ Ituma, E. A. *Basic Research Guide for Humanities and Social Sciences* (6th Edition) (Society for Research and Academic Excellence Nsukka), (2019), p.39.

⁸ Ibid. 2.

⁹ Qur'an, 27:22-23.

¹⁰ Tillier, M. *Women before the qādī under the Abbasids*. *Islamic Law and Society*, 2009, 16, pp.280-301. ffhalshs-00582725f

- ¹¹Wagner, M. M. "The Decline of Women's Rights in Turkey: Is it Political Islam...or Tayyip?" Undergraduate Honors Theses. Paper 1069, (2016).
- ¹² Shami, A. A. *Political Empowerment of Women in Pakistan*. Pakistan Vision, 10 no.1, (2013).
- ¹³ Fahm, A. O. *Muslim Women and the Nigerian Party Politics*. (March 2020).
- ¹⁴ Koburtay, T. Muhammad, A., Ahmed, A. A., Abuzaid, S. I. N. and Pattnaik, M. *Women Leadership, Culture, and Islam: Female Voices from Jordan*. *Journal of Business Ethics*, (2023): 183:347–363, 358.
- ¹⁵ United State Institute of Peace, *Tawakkol Karman: A Nobel Peace Prize Winner Reflects on Yemen Today* (<https://www.usip.org/events/tawakkol-karman-nobel-peace-prize-winner-reflects-yemen-today..2015>), 1.
- ¹⁶ Falola, T: *Valiancy, Advocacy and Resiliency* (<https://ntm.ng/2020/09/07/aisha-yesufu-valiancy-advocacy-and-resiliency/..2020>), 7.
- ¹⁷Alhussein, Z. R. *Universal Declaration of Human Right* (https://www.un.org/en/udhrbook/pdf/udhr_booklet_en_web.pdf, 2015), vii.
- ¹⁸ Rahman, F. N. and Memon, K. *Political Participation of Women: Contemporary Perspective of Gender and Islam*, *Weber Sociology & Anthropology*, 1, no. 1 (2021): 8.
- ¹⁹OIC, *The Cairo Declaration on Human Rights in Islam*. ([https://elearning.icrc.org/detention/en/story_content/external_files/Human%20Rights%20in%20Islam%20\(1990\).pdf](https://elearning.icrc.org/detention/en/story_content/external_files/Human%20Rights%20in%20Islam%20(1990).pdf).,1999), 1.
- ²⁰Patoari, M. H. *The Rights of Women in Islam and Some Misconceptions: An Analysis from Bangladesh Perspective*. (<https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation.aspx?paperid=96850>., 2019): 11.
- ²¹ Bukhari and Muslim, *The Book of Miscellany, Riyad as-Salihin*, (<https://sunnah.com/riyadussalihin>): 283.
- ²² Ibrahim, Z. *Reinstating the Queens: Reassessing the Hadith on Women's Political Leadership*. *American Journal of Islam and Society*, 33, no. 2 (2016): vi.
- ²³ Quran 9:71.